

Reaction Equilibrium of Lead Sulphate and Hydrochloric Acid

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The reaction $2\text{HCl}(\text{aq}) + \text{PbSO}_4(\text{S}) \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(\text{aq}) + \text{PbCl}_2(\text{S})$ has been studied in stoichiometric proportions at different initial concentrations of hydrochloric acid. Per cent conversion, solubility of lead sulphate and the heat of reaction have been determined.

In the previous paper¹ the reaction $2\text{HCl}(\text{aq}) + \text{PbSO}_4(\text{S}) \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(\text{aq}) + \text{PbCl}_2(\text{S})$ has been reported. Here an account of further study of the conversion of lead sulphate to sulphuric acid has been given.

PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

Pure hydrochloric acid diluted to desired strength at 30° and pure lead sulphate prepared from marine gypsum and lead chloride were used in stoichiometric proportions and the reaction was carried out with stirring for 1½ hr. in a closed glass vessel. After the reaction the liquor was filtered clear through sintered glass pipette, and analysed for total acidity, sulphate and chloride contents from which concentrations of hydrochloric and sulphuric acids in the mixture were calculated. Lead was estimated gravimetrically by chromate method and its microquantities determined colorimetrically using dithizone. Heat of reaction was calculated to be 2.5 KCal per mole of lead sulphate, from the temperature rise of 9.5° over the initial 30° during the reaction in an insulated reaction vessel, heat of wetting of lead sulphate in water being less than 0.09 calories per 52.9 m² area² was neglected.

Results are expressed as (1) sulphuric acid formed in the equilibrium liquor, (2) the reaction (per cent conversion) of hydrochloric acid to sulphuric acid and (3) lead (Pb⁺⁺) content in equilibrium liquor at 30° in a stoichiometric reaction and are plotted against the initial concentration of hydrochloric acid (Fig. 1). The curves for (1) and (2) on extrapolation touch the hydrochloric acid initial concentration axis at 3.8 moles per 100 moles of water, corresponding to 7% hydrochloric acid concentration, indicating that the reaction may completely stop below that concentration of hydrochloric acid.

It is also observed that the lead (Pb⁺⁺) content of the equilibrium liquor after the reaction, increases with dilution of its hydrochloric acid content. In other words, use of lower initial concentration of hydrochloric acid is accompanied by more loss of lead in the equilibrium liquor. During distillation of the liquor, lead is recovered as it precipitates

1. A. N. Kappanna and B. P. Choudhari, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, 26, 91.
2. W. A. Kohler and J. H. Mathews, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1158.

out as lead sulphate with decrease in the concentration of hydrochloric acid. When sulphuric acid attains concentration of 55 per cent all the hydrochloric acid is expelled out and all the lead is also precipitated out making the sulphuric acid free from chloride and lead.

INITIAL CONCENTRATION OF HCl IN MOLES PER 100 MOLES OF WATER

N.B.:—The graphs refer to quantities (1) H_2SO_4 formed ($\frac{1}{2}$ moles), (2) Reaction (percent conversion), and (3) Lead (Pb^{++}) content in $\times 10^{-3}$ g. per 100 g. of equilibrium liquor plotted against initial concentration of HCl in moles per 100 moles of water at $30^\circ C$.

Fig. 1. Reaction of lead sulphate and hydrochloric acid at $30^\circ C$.

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